

Determinant Factors of Flooding Frequency and Severity in Afafanyi, Abi Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study identifies and accounts for the factors responsible for flooding in Afafanyi in Abi Local Government Area of Cross River State using the cross-sectional survey research design method. The target population comprised the individuals, community leaders, religious leaders, youth leaders, health centre workers, and school owners in the community. From the total population of 18,000 in the study area, a sample size of 400 was determined using the Taro-Yamane formula. Of the 400 copies of the questionnaire administered and retrieved, 390 that were properly filled out were analysed. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed for data presentation and analysis. Results showed that 64.8% agreed that the weak drainage capacity of the water channel caused by the blocked drains contributed to the flood disaster in the study area. Findings showed that anthropogenic development along flood drains and drainage facilities was the major factor responsible for the flood disaster in the study area. The study further revealed that failure to heed flood warnings exacerbated vulnerability to floods. Thus, the study concludes that a large proportion of the households in the community are vulnerable to flood disasters due to the location of their structures in flood-prone areas. Based on the findings, the work recommended that government and relevant agencies and organizations, should as a matter of necessity organize enlightenment programmes to educate the public on the dangers of flood disaster and its causes highlighting the adverse effects of indiscriminate dumping of refuse in gutters, drainage and river channels, government should set up various information programmes to educate the public on the way to respond to flood events.

Keywords: *Anthropogenic, flood, water channel, emergency management, drainage.*

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Introduction

Flooding remains one of the many environmental problems that threatens the world. It is considered to be the most devastating natural disasters worldwide (Komolafe et al. 2015), occurring when water bodies

rise into areas above their normal levels (Adinna, 2001). All water bodies, either stagnant or flowing, have their containing levels, while Rivers flowing into channels and oceans have their basins. In most developing countries, flooding results from climate change, excessive precipitation, building on water ways, sea-level rise, soil moisture regime, dam operations, especially along borders, uncontrolled rapid population growth, inadequate preparedness, and a lack of political will to respond to the problem promptly. According to Agbonkhese et al (2014), excessive or heavy precipitation is a major cause of flooding and also climate change and anthropogenic activities (Umar, & Gray, 2022).

Just as the concept of vulnerability is at the centre of discourse in environmental risk, climate change and environmental degradation, so is the issue of what extent, how and who is vulnerable to flooding in the study area under consideration here. The consensus among scholars is that vulnerability measures the level/extent to which a natural or social system is susceptible to sustain damage from climate change, environmental degradation and environmental risk (Mfon et al. 2022, Ojikpong et al, 2016). Furthermore, vulnerability is largely determined by the development context which has a strong influence on household's income, education and access to information on people's exposure to environmental hazards in their homes and workplaces on the quality and extent of provision for infrastructure and services (Mfon et al. 2022). While vulnerability describes the potential for loss due to a particular hazard, it also reveals the elements at risk (Njoku et al, 2020; Mfon et al. 2022).

It therefore follows that flood vulnerability explains the degree/extent to which a person, people or place are at risk of flooding and its adverse effects (Mfon et al. 2022). It explains the likelihood of an area to be submerged by water and the elements that are at risk to be affected. In most cases flooding affects housing units and agricultural lands further resulting in economic problems (Mfon et al. 2022). It was reported that the flood which occurred as a result of the downpour from rain that lasted for about five days, submerged the affected communities, destroying rice, yam, and cassava farms, economic trees, household items, as well as schools worth millions of Nigeria Naira in the River communities of Obubra LGA.. Besides, the heavy rain further affected economic activities and vehicular movements, with residents of the affected areas seen evacuating their children to nearby neighbourhoods as well as removing household items to safer places (Okoro, 2022).

It is in light of the foregoing, that this study seeks to escalate in this paper issues concerning the perennial challenges of flooding and the threats to lives, properties, businesses, and damage to vital infrastructure, disruption of essential public services, as well as identify the factors responsible and proffer flood management strategies and actionable mitigation measures for flooding in the study area of Afafanyi in Abi Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Theoretical, Conceptual and Empirical Review

Emergency Management Theory

According to this theory, a hazard is more likely to cause a disaster when planning is haphazard, policies are not enforced, disaster management equipment is underdeveloped, preparedness measures are ignored, and when there are challenges facing institutions and the special populations or other at-risk groups (George et al., 2011). Such theoretical constructs are useful in understanding the nature of disasters and the difficulty of successful emergency management operations (Muriithi, 2021). This is especially against the backdrop of the emergency management that seeks to promote safer, less vulnerable communities with the capacity to cope with hazards and disasters (McEntire, 2021; MEMA, 2020). Nonetheless, the compliance to disaster management policies, mitigation strategies, preparedness to respond, and recovery have played a significant role in categorizing distinct emergency management functions (Muriithi, 2021).

It has been suggested that in promoting emergency management theory, there is need to not only retain the findings from prior research in the field, which include concepts such as disaster, hazard, convergence, and emergence, but scholars should accept new concepts such as “compound disasters”

and “sustainability” as a way to illustrate the complexity of modern disasters and the need for environmental protection. It equally argued for further inclusion into the emergency management theory must such principles as disaster prevention, preparedness and improvisation (Rubin, 2000; McEntire & Marshall, 2003; McEntire, 2005).

Further perspectives for improved emergency management theory by McEntire (2005) had suggested the integration of research from each of the contributing disciplines, such that the students would appreciate the diversity of issues and functions to be addressed in the field. According to him, such should include, but are not limited to:

“hazard and vulnerability analysis, land-use planning, engineering, planning, training, exercising, community education, grant acquisition, budgeting, warning, evacuation, sheltering, fire suppression, emergency medical care and triage, search and rescue, mass fatality management, media relations, disaster declaration, donations management, debris management, critical incident stress management, etc” (Smith, 1992; Rubin, 2000; McEntire, 2005).

In summary, disasters and the theory of emergency management have remain vibrant subjects of discuss for scholars and researchers deploying a variety of methods, including observation, field research, and comparison, among others. They have focused on a variety of topics, including the definition of disasters, human behavior in extreme events, the nature of emergency management, ways to make the profession more effective, the pros and cons of various paradigms, and new areas of research (McEntire, 2021).

Concept of Vulnerability

Several scholars have attempted to conceptualise the term “vulnerability” in various ways, hence the diverse perspectives that the subject matter of vulnerability accommodates (Berezi, et al 2019; Amama, et al, 2023). For instance, USAID (2011) defines vulnerability as the characteristics and circumstances of a community system or asset that make it susceptible to the damaging effects of a hazard. For other, it is a set of prevailing or consequential conditions arising from various physical, social economic and environmental factors which increase the susceptibility of a community to impacts of hazards (UNISDR, 2009; 2015; Endumeni Local Municipality, 2022). Chambers (1989) viewed vulnerability in terms of internal/external perspective proposing that “vulnerability has two sides: an external side of risks, shocks, and stress to which an individual is subject to; and an internal side which is defenseless, meaning a lack of means to cope without damaging loss. Loss can take many forms-becoming or being physically weaker, economically impoverished, socially dependent, humiliated or physically harmed” (UNISDR, 2009 & UNISDR, 2015).

Furthermore, UNDRR (2017) defined Vulnerability as:

‘The conditions determined by physical, social, economic, and environmental factors or processes which increase the susceptibility of an individual, a community, assets, or systems to the impacts of hazards’.

A society or community’s level or pattern of vulnerability is determined by historical, political, cultural, institutional, and natural resource processes that shape people's lives and lifestyles, that may produce a range of underlying drivers of vulnerability (UNDRR, 2017;WHO, 2022). This includes living in disaster risk areas or in poor housing, ill-health, political tensions, or a lack of local institutions or preparedness measures (Saulnier, et al 2022).

This equally implies that all communities and countries are at risk of being exposed to disasters which is directly associated with the resilience or susceptibility of individuals and communities to hazardous events. Understanding and identifying individual or community vulnerability is important for developing and implementing Disaster Risk Management (DRM) policies and programmes to reduce disaster risk and increase resilience in communities (WHO, 2022). From the foregoing, (UNDRR, 2017 & WHO, 2022) ascertains that vulnerability is important for determining disaster health risk for communities and people. Disaster risk does not only depend on disaster severity or the number of people affected, but also on people’s susceptibility to the disaster impact. So, understanding levels of vulnerability in relation to

hazard exposure helps to explain why some hazards result in severe impacts, while others don't (UNISDR, 2015 & UNDRR, 2017)

Furthermore, it is the view of Damas & Rayhen (2004) that vulnerability is exposure to contingencies, shocks, stress, and difficulty in coping with them. The shock being caused by vulnerability are commonly related to illness and death, natural disasters, state failure and economic collapse (Chronic Poverty Report 2004-2005). Ireland et al (2004) stated that “livelihoods are vulnerable when they are unable to cope with or respond to exposure to risks, stresses and shocks”. While the World Health Organization (2000) described vulnerability as the degree to which a population, individual or organization is unable to anticipate, cope with, resist and recover from impacts of disasters, other scholars have linked the concept to climate change.

For instance, the old weather plan for England which sought to protect the health and reduce the harm from cold weather, put in place by the UK Department of Health in 2018 (DOH, 2018), noted that the health risks and impacts resulting from cold weather greatly affect the most vulnerable people in society, such as children, older people and the chronically ill patients. This is premised on how excessive exposure to cold temperatures or weather can increase the risk of respiratory infections, stroke, heart attack and hypothermia, for which these categories of gender are usually most affected (Saulnier, et al 2022). The replicate in Nigeria can be linked to how these group in the population found in the flood prone areas are also mostly affected flooding. For this, Clark et al (2000) define vulnerability “as the risk of adverse outcomes to receptors and exposure units (human groups, ecosystems and communities) in the face of relevant changes in the climate, other environmental variables and social conditions, and not without the consequences of instability associated with flooding frequency, severity, and impacts (See Figure 1).

Figure 1. Thresholds for the Stability of People in Floods

Notes: $D.V = VxD = \text{velocity} \times \text{depth}$

Concept of Flooding

Flood or flooding as a concept is not new, but has become very topical that several scholars have given several definitions of flooding. Flood is usually used as a general term to describe the overflow of water from a stream channel into normally dry land in the floodplain (riverine flooding), higher-than-normal levels along the coast and in lakes or reservoirs (coastal flooding) as well as ponding of water at or near the point where the rain fell (flash floods) (IRDR 2014; United Nations in Indonesia; 2025). The excess overflows the banks and spreads out to the surrounding lands, producing the flood condition. According to Resonzweig (2009), flood can be defined as an unusual accumulation of water above the ground, which is caused by high tides, heavy rainfall, or rapid runoff from paved surfaces. Some rivers are known to

have natural floodplains, while the most serious floods occur along coastal areas. In these areas, heavy rainfall and poor soil combine to cause flooding. Hendrick (2007) thus defines flood as any overland flow over urban land sufficient to cause significant property damage, traffic obstruction, nuisance, and health hazards (iProject Download, n.d.).

Also, flood has been described to occur when more water is brought into a drainage channel than the channel can carry. This coincides with the definition put up by Ajayi (1997). Daniel and Udo (2019) agree with the opinion of Ward (1989) that a flood is an overflowing body of water overland, not normally submerged. In their definition, Jeb and Aggarwal (2008) stated that flooding is a general temporal condition of partial or complete inundation of normally dry areas from overflow of inland or tidal waters or from unusual and rapid accumulation of runoff. According to Mfon et al. 2022, there are three different perspectives on vulnerability. The first measures vulnerability in terms of exposure to hazardous events and the influence that such events have on people and structures, the second characterizes vulnerability as it affects human relationships, while the third perspective views vulnerability as both physical events and the underlying causal characteristic of the population that leads to risk exposure and limited capacity of communities to respond. These three are often evident concerning vulnerable areas to flooding in the cities and towns, especially in developing countries (Mfon et al. 2022).

Materials and Methods

The Study Area

The study area is Afafanyi and environs in Abi Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. Abi is one of the eighteen (18) Local Government Areas in Cross River State and is located politically within the central Senatorial District of the State. Abi LGA lies approximately between latitude 50 45' 47" and 60 00' 58" N of the equator and longitude 70 45' 39" E and 80 06' 07" E of Greenwich Meridian (Figures 2). The Local Government Area is bounded in the north and west by Ebonyi State, it is bounded to the east by Yakurr Local Government Area, and to the South by Biase Local Government Area of Cross River State. Abi comprises two major tribes – the Bahumono and Agbo. Among villages in Bahumono are Anong, Ediba, Usumutong, Ebijakara, Ebom, Bazohure, Igoni Goni, Afafanyi, and Abe-Ugo (Emri, Okpe, & Oko, 2019).

Figure 2. Abi LGA Showing the Various Communities.

Source: Department of Survey, Calabar (2024)

Materials and Methods

This study adopted a cross-sectional research design and generated its data through a survey through a mixed-method that combined both the quantitative and qualitative approaches, in-depth Informant interviews (IDIs), and a cross-sectional descriptive study (quantitative survey) to assess the socio-economic impacts of flood and community coping strategies in the study area. The population of the study comprises the entire population of the Afafanyi community of Abi Local Government Area of Cross River State, in which impacted and vulnerable communities in the seventeen (17) LGAs in Abia State were selected. The target population were the individuals, community leaders, religious leaders, youth leaders, health centre workers, and school owners in the community. From a total population of 18,000 for the study area, sample size of 400 was determined using the Taro-Yamane formula. Out of the 400 copies of the questionnaire administered and retrieved, 390 were properly filled and hence analyzed using the descriptive and inferential statistics, and presented in frequency tables, graphs, and charts.

Results and Discussion

Factors Responsible for Flooding in Afafanyi

This study revealed that both natural and anthropogenic factors are responsible for flooding in the study area. As regards natural causes, 78.4% of the respondents affirmed heavy rainfall to be the main cause of flooding in the area. 15.7% stated that flooding is caused by overflow from the river, while storm surge (4%) and will of God (1.9%) are affirmed responsible for flooding. This is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Natural Causes of Flooding in the Study Area

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Heavy rainfall	294	78.8
Overflow from river	59	15.7
Storm surge	15	4.0
Will of God	7	1.9
Total	375	100

Identification of Anthropogenic Activities Causing Flood in Afafanyi

Regarding knowledge of anthropogenic factors causing floods, separate questions on specific items were administered. From the responses presented in Table 2, 64.8% respondents affirmed that the the blockage of the channel which contributed to flooding was due to the weak drainage capacity in the area. While 35.2% said “No”. on whether development along flood drains and drainage facilities is responsible for flooding, 72.3% answered in the affirmative while 27.7% did not think so. When responding to the question on whether massive deforestation increases flood vulnerability, a disproportionate 80.8% of the respondents stated that it is true, while only 19.2% did not agree. 68.5% of the participants agreed that indiscriminate dumping of waste and debris along natural drainage channels is an anthropogenic activity, 64.8% affirmed failure to heed flood warnings as an activity causing vulnerability to floods, while 65.6% admitted that increased urbanization with expansion of urban structures close to the river channels exacerbates vulnerability to floods.

Table 2. Knowledge of Anthropogenic Activities Causing Flooding in the Community

Statement	Responses - Yes	Percentage %	Response - No	Percentage %
Blockage of drainage channel resulting from its weak capacity	243	64.3	132	35.2

Physical development along drainage facilities	271	72.3	104	27.7
Massive and fast paced deforestation increases flood vulnerability	303	80.8	72	19.2
Indiscriminate dumping of waste Debris along natural drainage channels	257	68.5	118	31.5
Failure to heed flood Warnings	243	64.8	132	35.2
Increased urbanization with expansion of urban structures close to river channels	246	65.6	129	34.4

Factors Influencing the Extent of Community Resilience

Table 3 depicts the analysis of factors affecting the extent of community resilience to flooding in the study area. Results showed that 75.2% of the respondents affirm that housing units, shelters, business/industries, and critical infrastructures' geographical location influences the resilience of the community to flood. Again, while 80.8% of the respondents agreed that availability of social networks facilities (electricity, water, telephone) is a vital factor in the community resilience building, 76.3% of the respondents affirmed that physical infrastructure such as communication and transport facilities, dams and levees, roads and bridges, constitute the essential factors for community resilience (Berezi, & Nwankwoala, 2022). Furthermore, 85.4% agreed that information and knowledge acquired from past experiences concerning floods shared with neighbours, friends, and relatives influences the resilience of communities (Berezi, & Nwankwoala, 2022). The majority of the respondents affirm that educational levels, livelihood patterns (type of education and income level), and availability of non-governmental organizations influence the resilience of communities to floods.

Table 3. Community Resilience to Flooding

Responses	SA	A	N	D	SD
Geographical location of housing units' business and industries, shelters/ critical infrastructures influence resilience of communities	180 (48)	102 (27.2)	23 (6.1)	57 (15.2)	13 (3.5)
Availability of social networks (electricity, water, telephone) is vital factor in community resilience building	169 (45.1)	134 (35.7)	19 (5.1)	45 (12)	8 (2.1)
Access to physical infrastructure like roads, bridges, dams and levees as well as communication and transport facilities are essential factors for community resilience	181 (48.3)	105 (28)	45 (12)	35 (9.3)	9 (2.4)
Information and knowledge acquired from past experiences concerning floods shared with neighbour's friends and relatives influence resilience of communities	184 (49.1)	136 (36.3)	33 (8.8)	16 (4.3)	6 (1.6)
Educational level influences resilience influences resilience	192 (51.2)	125 (33.3)	19 (5.1)	27 (7.2)	12 (3.2)
Livelihood pattern (type of employment, income level influences resilience. Availability of Non Governmental Organizations (NGOs) also influences resilience	183 (48.8)	131 (34.9)	29 (7.7)	23 (6.1)	9 (2.4)
Neighbours' friends and relatives support contribute to communityresilience	133 (35.5)	174 (46.6)	32 (8.5)	26 (6.9)	10 (2.7)

Awareness of the Risk of Floods in the Locality

The result obtained and presented in Table 4 shows that 99.5 % of the respondents affirmed that they are aware of the risk of floods in the area, while an insignificant 5% said No.

Table 4. Awareness of the Risk of Flood in the Community

Responses	Frequency	Rate
Yes	373	99.5
No	2	0.5
Total	375	100

Why People Live in the Area Despite their Awareness of the Risk of Floods?

The respondents attributed their continued stay in the flood prone areas in the community to varied reasons. While 40% of the respondents admitted that their reason for continued stay in these areas is because of closeness to their livelihoods, 16% affirmed access to amenities as their reason. 12.8% of the respondents stated their reason for their continued stay to cultural affinity to the land. Incidentally, the same percentage of the respondents (12.8%) affirmed their reason to be the need to preserve and maintain home grounds. 8% of the respondents do not feel the need to vacate the area because their experience is that the floods are always of short duration. 8% of the respondents stated they have no option as they cannot afford alternative accommodation. This position is illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Why People still Live in the Flood Risk Areas?

Underlying Causes of Vulnerability to Floods

Table 6 below reveals the causes of vulnerability to floods. Results shows that 78.7% respondents were of the opinion that residing in the flood-prone area, lack of substitute livelihoods (12.8%), poverty (6.7%), and health always (1.8%) were the causes of vulnerability to floods by individuals and the community.

Table 6. Underlying Causes of Vulnerability to Floods

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Residing in flood prone areas	295	78.7
Lack of alternative livelihoods	48	12.8
Poverty	25	6.7
Health challenges	7	1.8
Total	375	100

Source: Researcher’s Fieldwork (2024)

Frequency of Flood Occurrence

Table 7 reveals that 90.6% of the respondents affirm that flood incidences happen on a yearly basis, while 4%, 3.2 % and 2.1% respondents stated that flood incidences occur every 2 years, every 5 years, and every 10 years, respectively.

Figure 6. Knowledge of the Frequency of Flood Occurrence

Magnitude of the 2022 Flood in Terms of Depth of Flood Waters (Flood Height)

As Table 8 revealed, 22.7% of the respondents affirmed that the depth of the 2022 flood was equivalent to the ankle, 44.5% affirmed it was up to knee height, 20.8% stated it was over the knee height, while 12% stated they did not know.

Table 8. Magnitude of the 2022 Flood in the Community in Terms of Depth of Flood Waters (Flood Height)

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Equivalent to ankle	85	22.7
Knee height	167	44.5
Over the knee	78	20.8
No knowledge	45	12.0
Total	375	100

Magnitude (Depth) of the 2012 and 2022 Floods Compared

Comparing the 2012 and 2022 flood magnitudes as shown in Table 9, 67.2% respondents were of the opinion that the 2022 flood was more than the 2012 flood, while 24.8% the respondents said they were of the same magnitude. 4.8% percent of the respondents said they have no idea. On the duration of floods each year, 67.5% of the respondents said that it is between 1-3 months, 30.4% said it was below 1 month, while 2.1% stated it was above 3 months.

Table 9. Comparison of the Depth of the 2022 Flood with that of the 2012 Flood

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Higher	252	67.2
Less	93	24.8
Same height	12	3.2
No idea	18	4.8
Total	375	100

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork (2024)

Flood Susceptibility Analysis

Several factors and indicators that determines to a very great extent flood susceptibility were analysed in this section. They range from socio-economics, physical and environmental factors. Specific examples include data on location characteristics, infrastructure, building structures, population density, and other social and economic indicators.

Type of Dwelling for the Household

Table 10 reveals that the house type predominant in the area is cement block-walls built with a concrete floor and corrugated iron sheet or long span aluminum sheets with timber members. 99% of the buildings were those built with cement block-walls, while those with mud-walls and wooden walls together made up 1%.

Table 10. Flood Susceptibility in the Area

Type of building for household	Frequency	Percentage
Cement block walls concrete floor and corrugated iron sheet, long span aluminum sheets	371	99
Mud walls, mud floor with wood and thatched roof	2	0.5
Wooden walls with C. I. S. roof on timber members	2	0.5
Total	375	100

Means of Communicating Flood Information and Level of Information Available about the Flood Threat

Results in Table 11 shows that 58.9% said that they got flood information communicated to them through the traditional method, 23.2% said it was through the radio, and 10.4% said it was through the television. Also, on the level of information available to them concerning the flood threats, an overwhelming 97.1% of the respondents attest to the fact that they are often informed of flood threats before they occur. From the analysis, traditional means of dissemination of information recorded the highest percentage of 58.9% followed by the radio (23.2%) television (10.4%), and mobile /internet (7.5%).

Figure 7. Means of Communicating Information on Flood

Level of Preparedness for the Floods

In view of the announcements in different media of the impending flood, 84.5% respondents affirmed they were prepared, while 15.5% of the respondents did not bother. Analyzing how the respondents

prepared for the floods, 2.7% of the respondents affirmed building an alternative house to live in, 33.3% and 21.6% respectively opted to take shelter with relatives and friends, 26.9% attest to elevating their compound with sand as a preventative measure to tackle the flood menace, while 15.5% affirmed being unprepared. (Table 12 and Table 13).

Table 12. Whether You were Prepared for the Floods

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	317	84.5
No	58	15.5
Total	375	100

Figure 8. Ways in which You were Prepared for the Flood

Assistance Obtained from the Government/Other Institutions during and after the Floods

Table 14: Presents the analysis of relief assistance donated to flood victims. The result disclosed that 94.7% of the respondents confirmed receiving assistance from government or other institutions in the course of the floods. On the type of assistance received by the victims of the flood hazard, 71.5% of the respondents affirmed they received food items, while 8.5% said they received a financial grant. This is depicted in Table 14, while Figure 9 shows the type of Assistance Received

Table 14. Whether Assistance was Received During/After the Floods

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	355	94.7
No	20	5.3
Total	375	100

Figure 9. Type of Assistance Received

Assessment of Government's Response

Regarding the government's timely response, 41.6% admitted it was belated, 16.8% said it was immediate, 28% expressed the opinion that it was inadequate, while 18.6% affirmed it was adequate. Shows in Table 15.

Figure 10. Assessment of Government Response

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study found that flood in Afafanyi and environs in Abi Local Government Area of Cross River State is caused by both natural and anthropogenic factors, which often lead to disasters. It was strongly agreed that the heavy rainfall, poor drainage capacity, blockage of water channel facilities, massive deforestation, and failure to heed flood warnings are factors responsible for the flood disaster in Afafanyi and environs in Abi Local Government Area of Cross Rivers State.

Based on the outcome of the study, it recommends the strengthening of relevant public agencies, other organizations, and stakeholders to catalyze enlightenment campaigns on the ubiquitous dangers and impacts of flood disaster, its causes and the sustainable response strategies and mechanism required to manage the menace. Such enlightenment campaigns should highlight among others, the adverse effects of indiscriminate dumping of refuse in gutters, irregular de-silting of drains and river channels since they constitute major drivers of flooding in the study area.

References

- Adinna, E. N. (2001). *Environmental hazards and management*. SNAAP Press.
- Agbonkhese, O., Agbonkhese, E. G., Aka, E. O., Joe-Abaya, J., Ocholi, M., & Adekunle, A. (2014). Flood menace in Nigeria: Impacts, remedial and management strategies. *Civil and Environmental Research*, 6(1), 32–40.
- Ajayi, M. S. I. (1997). *An analysis of external debt and capital flight in the severely indebted low income countries in sub-Saharan Africa* (Working paper). International Monetary Fund.
- Berezi, O. K., & Nwankwoala, H. O. (2022). Influence of community resilience to flood risk and coping strategies in Bayelsa State, Southern Nigeria. *Advances in Hydrology & Meteorology*, 1, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.33552/AHM.2022.01.000513>

- Berezi, O. K., Obafemi, A. A., & Nwankwoala, H. O. (2019). Flood vulnerability assessment of communities in the flood prone areas of Bayelsa State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Geology and Earth Sciences*, 5, 19–36.
- Chambers, R. (1989). Editorial introduction: Vulnerability, coping and policy. *IDS Bulletin*, 20(2), 1–7.
- Clark, W. C., Jaeger, J., & Roger, R. C. (2000). *Assessing vulnerability to global environmental risks* (Unpublished manuscript).
- Daniel, E. E., & Udo, R. (2019). Human-environment interactions. In E. Ibok, E. Daniel, & O. Atakpa (Eds.), *The politics of global environmental policies*. University of Calabar Press.
- Dow, K. (1992). Exploring differences in our common future(s): The meaning of vulnerability to global environmental change. *Geoforum*, 23, 417–436.
- Emri, S. I., Okpe, A. P., & Oko, E. E. (2019). Spatial distribution of primary healthcare facilities in Abi LGA of Cross River State–Nigeria. *International Journal of Agriculture, Environment and Bioresearch*, 4(1), 86–100.
- Endumeni Local Municipality. (2022). *Final 2021/2022 integrated development plan review*.
- George, G., Corbishley, C., Khayesi, J. N., Haas, M. R., & Tihanyi, L. (2016). Bringing Africa in: Promising directions for management research. *Academy of Management Journal*, 59(2), 377–393.
- iProject Download. (n.d.). *Socio-economic effect of flooding on wetlands*. Retrieved January 29, 2026, from <https://www.iprojectdownload.com/socio-economic-effect-of-flooding-on-wetlands/>
- Ireland, C., Sibanda, I., Mupetesi, T., & Mhlanga, S. (2004). *Livelihood insights: Challenges and trends in Zimbabwe with case studies from Matabeleland and Mashonaland*. World Vision Zimbabwe.
- Komolafe, A. A., Adeboyege, S. A., & Akinluyi, F. O. (2015). [Article title not provided]. *American Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 11(3), 157–166.
- Maine Emergency Management Agency. (2020). *What is emergency management?* Retrieved January 29, 2026, from Maine Emergency Management Agency website.
- McEntire, D. A. (2005). The status of emergency management theory: Issues, barriers, and recommendations for improved scholarship. *Journal of Emergency Management*, 3(3). <https://doi.org/10.5055/jem.2005.0031>
- McEntire, D. A., & Marshall, M. (2003). Epistemological problems in emergency management: Theoretical dilemmas and implications. *ASPEP Journal*, 10, 119–129.
- Mfon, I. E., Oguike, M. C., Eteng, S. U., & Etim, N. M. (2022). Causes and effects of flooding in Nigeria: A review. *East Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 1(9), 1777–1792.
- Mfon, I. E., Oguike, M. C., Eteng, S. U., & Etim, N. M. (2022). Causes and effects of flooding in Nigeria: A review. *International Journal of Social Science and Human Research*, 5(10). <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v5-i10-16>
- Muriithi, A. I. (2021). *Disaster management systems and level of preparedness at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya* (Master's project, Department of Security Studies and Correction Sciences, School of Security, Diplomacy and Peace Studies, Kenyatta University). Kenyatta University Institutional Repository.
- Njoku, C. J., Effong, J., & Ayara, N. (2020). A geospatial expose of flood risk and vulnerable areas in Nigeria. *International Journal of Applied Geospatial Research*, 11(3), 87–110.
- Ojikpong, B. E., Ekeng, E. E., Obongha, U. E., & Emri, S. I. (2016). Flood risk assessment of residential neighbourhoods in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State, Nigeria. *Environment and Natural Resources Research*, 6(2), 115–127.

- Okoro, J. (2022, August 19). *Flood kills 6, submerges 400 houses, 700 farms in Cross River*. *The Sun Nigeria*.
- Rosenzweig, E. D. (2009). A contingent view of e-collaboration and performance in manufacturing. *Journal of Operations Management*, 27(6), 462–478.
- Rubin, C. B. (2000). Emergency management in the 21st century: Coping with Bill Gates, Osama bin-Laden, and Hurricane Mitch (Natural Hazards Working Paper No. 104). Institute of Behavioral Science, Natural Hazards Research and Applications Information Center, University of Colorado Boulder.
- Smith, F. (2017). *How are people affected by floods?* Retrieved January 29, 2026, from Sciencing website.
- Smith, G. P., Davey, E. K., & Cox, R. J. (2014). *Flood hazard* (Technical Report 2014/07). Water Resources Laboratory, University of New South Wales.
- Smith, K. (1992). *Environmental hazards: Assessing risk and reducing disaster*. Routledge.
- Umar, N., & Gray, A. J. (2022). Flooding in Nigeria: A review of its occurrence and impacts and approaches to modelling flood data. *International Journal of Environmental Studies*, 80(7), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207233.2022.2081471>
- United Nations in Indonesia. (2025, September 16). *Flood – Definition and facts*. <https://indonesia.un.org/en/301573-flood-definition-and-facts>
- United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction. (2009). *Global assessment report on disaster risk reduction: Risk and poverty in a changing climate*. UNDRR.
- United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction. (2015). *Global assessment report on disaster risk reduction 2015: Making development sustainable, the future of disaster risk management*. UNDRR.
- United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction. (2017). *The Sendai Framework terminology on disaster risk reduction: Vulnerability*. Retrieved September 26, 2025, from UNDRR website.
- United States Agency for International Development. (2011). *USAID agency for sustainability policy statement*. USAID.
- Walesh, S. G. (1991). *Urban surface water management*. John Wiley & Sons.
- World Health Organization. (2002). *Environmental health in emergencies and disasters: A practical guide*. WHO.
- World Health Organization. (2022). *Disaster risk factors—Hazards, exposure and vulnerability* (WHO guidance on research methods for health emergency and disaster risk management, revised 2022). WHO.